

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	24 months

Deliverable information

WP	2
Deliverable related number	D2.2
Deliverable number	D4
Deliverable name	Website/Logo
Deliverable Description	Website/Logo
Lead Beneficiary	EAPM
Type	DEC
Dissemination level	Public
Version	Version 2
Due Date	31 Jan 2023
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Approval Date	

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Deliverable 4 – Website/Logo - Version 2

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
Version 1	14 Mar 2023	Request for revision comment: For both this deliverable and project website, please follow the rules for referencing EU funding as specified in your grant agreement.	EU - Katarina KREPELKOVA
Version 2	31 Mar 2023		

Authors	
Name	Partner
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Feedback from Colleagues	All Work Packages

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Feedback and input to webpages	All Work Packages

DELIVERABLE CONTENT

This document describes the design of the logo and development of the website for the CAN.HEAL project. The following steps were taken:

Date	Steps	Partner
21 Nov 2022	discussions with the designer, finalizing the logo	EAPM
02 Dec 2022	initial concept, framework	EAPM, Sciansano
12 Dec 2022	checking graphics, changing colors	EAPM
22 Dec 2022	preparing text, discussions, emails	EAPM
16 Jan 2023	reviewing content for the web - text and pictures	EAPM, Sciansano
31 Jan 2023	finalizing layout with the designer	EAPM
02 Feb 2023	final revision and touch-ups	EAPM

1.1 Logo

The main symbol is a combination of a cross as a symbol of help and an object that resemble a piece of code. Selected typography is a custom-made object. The solution is oriented towards the end users - patients.

1.2 Website edition 1.0 <https://canheal.eu/>

The website will be the core part of the communication/dissemination strategy for the CAN.HEAL project containing information on the partners, project, news (newsletter, events,...). See printscreens below.

KEY DEVELOPMENTS

Follow the key steps towards establishing recommendations for initiatives in the EU health system that will further improve the access of individuals and patients to prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of cancer through personalized medicine.

PROJECT OUTCOMES

Get familiar with Can.Heal project outcomes that will support the development of effective cancer prevention strategies and policies and implement personalised medicine approaches for all cancer patients in Europe.

PROJECT

Get to know the project in which 17 EU Countries joined to address two of the EBOP's initiatives: 'Cancer Diagnostic and Treatment for All' and 'Genomics for Public Health'. Genomics has become increasingly relevant in cancer medicine.

Can.Heal General Assembly Meeting

Internal meeting, Rome, 27th - 28th April 2023.

Events

- **Plenary Stakeholders Meeting**
Rome, 26th April 2023.
- **Can.Heal General Assembly Meeting / Internal**
Rome, 27th - 28th April

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Internal communication will be facilitated through the website by providing the link to the CAN.HEAL Sharepoint. The Platform is secured. Login and password are requested.

The Sharepoint is a platform to share documents and displays the calendar of the meetings:

Welcome to can.heal platform!

Documents

[+](#) new document or drag files here

- ✓ Name
- Templates and logo ...
- Contacts ...
- Kick-off meeting ...
- WPs ...
- Consortium agreement ...
- Grant agreement ...

Calendar

[+](#) new event or [edit](#) this list

✓	Date	Title	Location	End Time	All Day Event
	19/01/2023 13:00	Coordination meeting (coordinator & co-leads)	... Online	19/01/2023 14:00	
	26/01/2023 15:00	WP lead meeting	... Online	26/01/2023 17:00	
	26/04/2023 10:00	Stakeholder meeting	...	27/04/2023 13:00	
	27/04/2023 12:00	Plenary meeting	... Rome	28/04/2023 16:00	

